

EXPERIMENTAL

Treatment of Dimethylaniline with Iodic Acid and Iodine in presence of Glacial Acetic Acid.—To a well-cooled solution of dimethylaniline (30 ml) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) at 18° iodine (30 g.) and iodic acid (3 g.) were added with stirring during 30 min. The settled brown solution was decanted from unchanged iodine and iodic acid, made neutral with a strong solution of NaOH, and triturated until the solid product became granular. The violet solid (32g.) was collected after 12 hr., washed with water, and a portion of it was subjected to chromatographic resolution over alumina.

Chromatographic Separation of the Mixture.—The violet solid (2 g.) was taken in benzene (20 ml) and chromatographed on Brockmann alumina (4 × 20 cm). Elution was carried out with light petroleum, petrol-benzene (1:1), benzene, and benzene-methanol (1:1), 200 ml each, and 20-ml fractions were collected. Four compounds were isolated in pure form and the course of separation was traced in the following way (Table I).

TABLE I

Fractions.	Wt.	M.P.	$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$
1-4	0.03 g.	68°	..
7-12	1.17	75°	..
21-30	0.24	203-13°	578-82m μ
31-37	0.15	222-25°	545-52

N-p-Dimethylaminobenzyl-N-methylaniline.—The residue from fractions 1-4 was crystallised from dilute ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 68°. (Found: N, 11.58. Calc. for C₁₆H₂₀N₂: N, 11.66%). The identity was further established by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (m.p. 67-68°), prepared according to the method of Fayadh *et al.*³

p-Iododimethylaniline.—The residue from fractions 7-12 on crystallisation from ethanol furnished colorless platelets, m.p. 77° (lit.¹ m.p. 78.5°). (Found: N, 5.56; I, 51.56. Calc. for C₈H₁₀NI: N, 5.66; I, 51.41%).

Pentamethylpararosanine.—Eluates of fractions 20-35 were combined and concentrated under reduced pressure and the resinous mass (0.24 g.) was then converted to the chloride with a drop of 2*N*-HCl. The violet dye was dissolved in minimum quantity of water, the aqueous solution cooled in ice, and then basified with NaOH pellets. The flocculent precipitate was immediately extracted with benzene (2 × 30 ml); the benzene extract was dried over NaOH pellets and kept in a dark place at the room temperature. The amount of the dye formed and the acid sensitivity of the dye reagent were checked by the method recommended by Ghosh and Palit.⁴

The Iodo Dye.—Fractions 31-37 were combined, acidified (pH ~2) with HCl, and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure when a bluish violet resinous mass was left (0.15g.). The compound exhibited $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 548-55 m μ and other properties²⁻⁴ expected of a basic dye of the Crystal violet type.

3. Venkataraman, "The Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes", Academic Press Inc., New York, Vol. II, 1952, p.719.

4. This *Journal*, 1964, 41, 507.

Iodic Acid Oxidation of p-Iododimethylaniline.—To *p*-iododimethylaniline (0.1 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), powdered iodic acid (1 g.) was added over a period of 30 min. The colour of the solution turned purple on keeping for 4 hr. The solution was decanted from excess iodic acid, cooled in ice, and basified with 10*N*-NaOH. The gummy precipitate was immediately extracted with benzene and the extract dried over NaOH pellets. The pale yellow benzene extract showed indicator properties and absorption maxima exactly similar to those of the iodo-dye obtained from the preceding experiment. Structure elucidation of the iodo-dye is in progress.

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